

Institutionalization of Heritage

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Abstract: Every now and then we discuss ‘heritage’. Heritage is a buzz word that buzzes like an eternal word to our senses. Almost every society today uses heritage as a significant phenomenon, a sacred term that is given the highest value. Almost anything and everything can be considered as a feature of heritage. Heritage is abundantly practiced and promoted. In a backdrop as such where heritage looms in the signboards of sites and objects representing a valuable past, often we forget that it is an organized practice which serves the interests of many. This article attempts to highlight how institutionalization of heritage has developed over a period in the world, is a reality across societies and, actively promoted by legislative measures. It shall also, touch upon the emergence of heritage in the world and, in India specifically with specific focus on cultural and natural heritage of the country.

Keywords: Heritage, Natural Heritage, Cultural Heritage, State, Institutionalization

Introduction

The 'making' of heritage is an important area to consider since heritage is not simply a given social reality but rather heritage is carefully selected, categorized, and produced for the masses to accept and revere as a sacred past. Many stakeholders are involved in the process of making heritage worthy of preservation and conservation. A lot of work and effort is put into this process of heritage making by the stakeholders. The past is made orderly and presentable in the form of heritage. Thus, heritage is produced or made which necessitates for one to understand what goes into the making process, and who is involved in its making.

Upon the realization that heritage features are at risk due to threats posed by the activities in modern societies by the nineteenth century, heritage lists were made in order to safeguard these features. Since the past is considered as distinct from the present, classification and selection of heritage products was carried out by the stakeholders for placing heritage as a significant social reality in the public sphere which not only instilled heritage value in the public but also led to an expansion of heritage conservation practices.

Even though various agencies are involved in the running of heritage sites, the role of the State in engaging with heritage making practices is unavoidably significant. Many heritage sites are owned and managed by the governing bodies. Some such sites are a major source of revenue generation for the State. If we look at the historical development of heritage, it can be found that heritage is

very much associated with the nation's building process. It was only in the nineteenth century under the developing narrative of nationalism that heritage emerged as a significant factor for promoting a nation's identity, often in the form of a glorified past. Almost nearly every State strives to safeguard the features signifying its past be it artefacts, historical monuments, natural heritage landscapes, etc. Along with the safeguarding of heritage products, the State asserted control and manipulation which also led to the redefinition of heritage. As mentioned by Jafari and Xiao (2016), those nation-states which were specifically subjected to colonial rule produce heritage to establish an identity and foster a sense of national pride. And use heritage as an instrument for building, social, cultural capital and advancing sustainable developmental practices.

Historical understanding on the origins of State control of heritage

Regarding the origins of state control of heritage, Harrison (2013) mentions about James Scott (1998) who refers to heritage as turning into a regulatory process associated with bureaucratic high modernist planning, one of a series of linked State projects of standardization and management in which the local came under increasingly centralized administration. Over the late nineteenth and twentieth centuries, legislation of heritage expanded. In United States of America, initially few private lobbying efforts to preserve and conserve aspects of natural and cultural heritage led to the establishment of a government department for the management of heritage on federal lands such as the National Park Service.

The Yellow Stone National Park which was established by an Act of Congress in 1872 is the world's first 'wild' area reserved for recreational purposes under the management of the United States Federal Government. Several other legislative Acts were made to manage heritage products by the State. It was not just a single department which was authorized under legislative measures to manage heritage features rather different departments were authorized for management under a fragmented system, for example, monuments of military significance to be managed by Secretary of War, National forests to be managed by the Department of Agriculture, etc. The Preservation of Historic Sites Act (1935) initiated a national policy for the public use of historic buildings, monuments, and objects which were of national significance for the inspiration and benefit of the people of the United States and a national survey to identify historic sites for inclusion within the national park system. Like the 1935 Act, another Act called the Wilderness Act (1964), allowed the National Park Service to gazette areas that would be conserved primarily for their conservation values, not necessarily on their values for recreation. Such legislative measures, according to Harrison (2013) led to the increasing number of legislating controls relating to heritage and equally led to many objects; places and landscapes being turned into as features of 'heritage' in the twentieth century. Like the United States, England equally experienced legislations on heritage with increased definitions of it through Acts such as the Ancient Monuments Protection Act (1882) which scheduled the monuments and provided guardianship for the State to own monuments and, damaging such properties were considered as a punishable offence. The destruction of monuments in the Second World War also led to major changes in the legislation and planning heritage places as well as creation and reinvigoration of departments during the 1940s. National Heritage Act (1983) was another Act in England which secured the preservation and enhancement of

conservation areas; and which also aimed at promoting public's knowledge and enjoyment of ancient monuments and historic buildings along with its preservation.

The above examples of heritage legislation in the United States and England, reflects at the historical development of State control over heritage and expansion of places or objects which were to be termed as heritage during the twentieth century. Since heritage first emerged in Europe and then later was adopted in other non-European countries, institutionalization or heritage legislation first began within Europe itself and, which later, came to be practiced in other parts of the world. State led heritage control and production of heritage sites considerably increased from the 1960s onwards. After this phase, another phase came into existence which is associated with post-war international organizations such as the United Nations.

International organizations and heritage

Organizations like the United Nations consider heritage as a universal right and they promote the maintenance of this right by promulgating the long-term protection and conservation of universally significant sites (Labadi, 2013, as cited by Jafari and Xiao, 2016). As stated by Smith (2006), the year 1972 is a noteworthy milestone in the development and institutionalization of the heritage discourse since in this very year, the UNESCO (United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization) adopted the World Heritage Convention, also called as the Convention Concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage, which established an international

agenda for the protection and conservation of sites of universal significance, and importantly confirmed the presence of ‘heritage’ as an international issue. In addition, the World Heritage Convention further institutionalized the nineteenth century conservation ethic and the ‘conserve as found’ ethos (p. 27). According to Ogino (2022), the Convention defines the value that can give rise to museological desire and the conditions in which it can be realized in the Operational Guidelines for the implementation of the World Heritage Convention. The value is clearly defined as Outstanding Universal Value. It means “cultural and/or natural significance which is so exceptional as to transcend national boundaries and to be of common importance for present and future generations of all humanity” (p. 15-16).

Under the terms of the Convention, an international non-governmental World Heritage Committee was formed with a three-fold function. It was to produce a World Heritage List of cultural and natural properties of ‘outstanding universal value’ from nominations submitted by State Parties (a term used by the WHC for a country which has ratified the 1972 Convention). The assessment of cultural heritage sites was to be undertaken for the WHC by the International Council on Monuments and Sites (ICOMOS), and natural heritage sites by the international Union for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources (IUCN). Secondly, from the accepted and inscribed properties, it was to produce a List of World Heritage in danger, for the purposes of emergency assistance. Thirdly, it was to administer a World Heritage Fund to assist needy State Parties in protecting their World Heritage properties. A logical fourth function was added later- monitoring the state of conservation of inscribed properties (Pocock, 1997, p. 260).

Currently, as of 2025, there are 196 State parties involved with the Convention. The State Parties in their respective countries identify, classify, and nominate properties for inscription on the World Heritage List. The protection, conservation and preservation, and also, the proper management of the nominated properties is pledged by the member of State Parties of the Convention. The State Parties agree to operate in an organized manner for heritage properties to be managed as per the planning measures and policies set accordingly by the Convention. Basically, the Convention acts as a higher body which links natural, cultural or mixed heritage properties in a single document and also provides funds to the ratified countries for the maintenance of heritage sites.

The World Heritage Convention defines heritage as cultural, natural, and mixed. The definitions are as follows:

Cultural Heritage:

- I. Monuments: architectural works, works of monumental sculpture and painting, elements or structures of an archaeological nature, inscriptions, cave dwellings and combinations of features, which are of outstanding universal value from the point of view of history, art or science;
- II. Groups of buildings: groups of separate or connected buildings which, because of their architecture, their homogeneity or their place in the landscape, are of outstanding universal value from the point of view of history, art or science;

- 1) Sites: works of man or the combined works of nature and man, and areas including archaeological sites which are of outstanding universal value from the historical, aesthetic, ethnological or anthropological point of view.

Natural Heritage:

- 2) Natural features consisting of physical and biological formations or groups of such formations, which are of outstanding universal value from the aesthetic or scientific point of view;
- 3) Geological and physiographical formations and precisely delineated areas which constitute the habitat of threatened species of animals and plants of outstanding universal value from the point of view of science or conservation;
- 4) Natural sites or precisely delineated natural areas of outstanding universal value from the point of view of science, conservation, or natural beauty.

Mixed Heritage:

According to paragraph 46 of the Operational Guidelines, properties shall be considered as “mixed cultural and natural heritage” if they satisfy a part or the whole of the definitions of both cultural and natural heritage laid out in Articles 1 and 2 of the convention’.

On the history of institutionalization of heritage in India

India had ratified the Convention in the year 1977 and in the present, we have a total of 43 world heritage sites, out of which 35 are cultural heritage sites, seven are natural, and one is a mixed heritage site. Many of the heritage sites in India have been tentatively listed in the World Heritage Site list and thus, awaits the designation of a World Heritage Site. If we look at the institutionalization of heritage in India historically, Allchin (1978) notes, awareness of monuments as heritage features in India only sprung up under colonial rule by the British officials serving in different parts of the East India Company during the latter part of the eighteenth century and, it was during this period that Indian Monuments were regarded as features of cultural heritage. Sir William Jones promoted this practice of giving heritage value to the monuments through tasks laid before the Asiatic Society of Bengal. This practice found expression in the publications of that time. Monuments were then classified and dated and were also meant to relate styles to one another.

Another figure, Sir James Fergusson who carried out a systematic study of Indian Architecture was keenly involved in studying these monuments. Even though awareness of heritage value of monuments developed in this period, conservation or preservation was hardly of any major interest. However, the Government did subsequently show interest in the preservation of outstanding monuments such as the appointment of the Taj Committee by the Governor General, the Earl of Minto or also known as Lord Minto and the sum of one lakh rupees which was meant for repairs. Apart from the Taj, repairs were later undertaken for other monuments like the Fatehpur-Sikri, Sikandra Fort, and the dome of Itmad-ud-Daulah. Still such practices could not be termed as conservation practices under a regular policy made for the monuments of India.

In 1861, a new era opened with the establishment of the Archaeological Survey of India which appointed a Director and assistants who were assigned to carry out explorations and recording of antiquities of all sorts. It was not until 1861 that conservation was of interest. Sir Alexander Cunningham conducted a series of excavations during this period. The case of the restoration of the Mahabodhi Shrine in Bodh Gaya can be mentioned here which was initially ignored of restoration and only upon the arrival of a Burmese mission concerning the condition of the Shrine later, led to the awakening of British interest upon which Beglar was assigned for restoration instead of the conservation of the structure itself. Others, including Fergusson, were critical of Beglar's work. However, this period can be considered as the first systematic attempt by the Government to conserve the monuments in India.

In 1873, the Central Government delegated the task of conservation to the Local (Provincial) Governments. The Centre was later appointed as a Curator of Ancient Monuments in 1880. Later, monographs and lists of monuments were made by the Government with short-term policies. The absence of long-term policies of conservation on the part of the Government resulted in a lack of guidance which left the monuments in a risky state. This situation only changed with Lord Curzon becoming the new Viceroy in 1899 whose enthusiasm in conserving and preserving the monuments led to the reorganization of the Archaeological survey under a new director General, John Marshall and which also, later resulted in the enactment of a new Act called as the Ancient Monuments Preservation Act (1904) which began by defining the monuments as any structure, erection or monument which is of historical archaeological or artistic interest. Under this definition, the site and adjoining land requiring fencing or to preserve it was included as well. The Local

Government, as per the Act, was empowered to declare an ancient monument to be a protected monument. The Act also laid down the procedures for entering into agreements between the Commission and the owner for custody, maintenance and preservation. It also mandated the powers of compulsory purchase which excluded any monument from wholly or partly used for any religious observations (Allchin, 1978, pp. 747-751).

Under the Ancient Monuments Preservation Act (1904), a conservation policy was formulated with the efforts of Sir John Marshall. A 1919 resolution classified and listed both protected and unprotected monuments on the basis of two criteria, their general state of repair and their ownership. A regular system of inspection and a code of practice was established for repairs to protected monuments. Marshall's Conservation Manual (1923) discussed the philosophy of conservation and stressed the need for preservation, maintenance, and intelligent selection of worthwhile monuments under protection. The conservation principle focused on authenticity, greater restoration of 'living' monuments which were still in use, archaeologists to refrain from the upkeep of religiously significant monuments as protected without the desires of its trustees or owners, and only in matters of exceptional archaeological interest, guidance and finance was to be provided for such monuments of religious observances. Special credit goes to the Ancient Monuments Preservation Act for safeguarding and protecting the monuments which can still be witnessed to this day in contemporary times. Subsequently, many other Acts were later formulated after the Independence of India such as the Ancient and Historical Monuments and Archaeological Sites and Remains (Declaration of National Importance) Act, 1951 which further empowered the Government to assert power over those owners of monuments who refused to enter into agreement with the Government, and could prohibit the construction of any buildings within the protected

areas or its vicinity areas. Basically, post-independence, the monuments were divided into four categories according to their ownership namely those under Central Government control, State Government control, Private or Corporate control without any protection or listed, and those which are subjects of agreement-based deals between the private owners and the archaeological department (Allchin, 1978). Thus, heritage legislation in India specifically in terms of cultural heritage dates to the colonial period and is a result of British intervention and creation of a heritage conservation landscape. However, apart from the legislation of cultural heritage-based features, conservation of natural heritage-based legislation equally finds significance in the overall conservation landscape of India.

Conservation and preservation of India's flora and fauna can be traced back to the pre-colonial era whereby evidences of legal provision for protecting the environment can be found in prolific ancient Indian texts like the Arthashastra by Kautilya, contribution of King Ashoka's 5th pillar edict which was the first documented conservation law in India, reverence of nature by different communities, etc. Here, however, special reference shall be made to the conservation landscape of the colonial era and the post-colonial era. It is stated that before the advent of the Britishers, India can be considered to have rich wildlife. The Britishers imposed new rules on the land which resulted in the decline of wildlife population. Although many Indian Rulers like Akbar and his game hunting (Gamargha Hunt) were earlier involved in the hunting of wildlife even before the Britishers set their foot in India, wildlife casualties in fact increased under the colonizers as they were also equally involved in hunting as a recreational activity similar to their fellow Indian Rulers with even more powerful or better hunting weapons. Colonial influence first started with the control of forest lands under the aegis of the East India Company through policies and legislations.

Both conservation and exploitation of wildlife ran parallel during the colonial period. During the initial phase of colonial rule, the administrators carried out imperial hunting and ordered the extermination of wild animals with a motive to clear wildlife inhabited areas and cultivate such areas for gaining revenue out of it. Such an exploitative approach to wildlife remained for the initial phase and later, slowly gave way to a different phase of colonial rule which focused on a sensitive approach towards wildlife. This sensitive approach led to the establishment of protected parks or wildlife sanctuaries and thus began the era of wildlife conservation in the nineteenth century.

Some of the legislative measures formulated by the British administrators for conservation purposes are the Indian Forest Act of 1878 which was to regulate the use of forests and wildlife, and the Arms Act of 1878 which regulated hunting by prohibiting the locals from using any weapons and use permits for engaging in small hunting. If we analyze both the Acts, systematic exploitation of natural resources for commercial purposes by gaining control over the forest areas by the colonial administrators can be observed which happened under the guise of legislative measures for rightful conservation. Such legislation gravely affected the local communities whose lives revolved around nature as they were unable to access the forests freely due to unjust colonial impositions.

The post-colonial period in India met with many changes when it comes to conservation policies. Acts like the Rhinoceros Preservation Act and the Elephant Preservation Act of the 1950s, the Indian Board of Wildlife (1952), Forest Conservation Act (1980), The Environmental Protection Act (1986), etc., are some of the Acts formulated after India's independence for protecting

endangered wildlife species. The Wildlife (Protection) Act of 1972 can be considered as the only Act formulated after the country's independence which provided a national conservation policy and led to the creation of national parks and wildlife sanctuaries for managing the depleting population of wildlife under a legal framework. It also created uniform legislation for the protection of wildlife across all the states, establishment of a network of parks and sanctuaries as protected areas and managing poaching or illegal wildlife trade. The two main conservation strategies of the Act are: protection of specified endangered species regardless of their location, and protection of all species in designated areas. The 1972 Act has so far undergone many amendments. The most recent amendment of the Wildlife Amendment Act, 1972 was made in the year 2022. The Rajya Sabha passed the Wildlife (Protection) Amendment Bill, 2022 which is aimed at fulfilling India's obligations under the Convention on International trade on Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES) which is basically an international agreement first drafted in 1963 by the International Union of Conservation and Nature (IUCN). The Bill's objectives include enhancing punishment for illegal wildlife trade, better management of protected areas along with local community well-being, and protection of forest lands.

Conclusion

Institutionalization of heritage thus developed in a step-by-step manner, first starting from Europe and then later, adapted in other parts of the world. Harrison (2013) rightly categorizes heritage into two types namely official heritage and unofficial heritage, respectively. According to him, some features of heritage are officially recognized as heritage products whereas those which are not

officially recognized by the State are regarded as unofficial heritage. Such recognition of sites as official heritage sites is supposed to undergo certain checks and classification to be considered as heritage products. Most States also prefer to include their heritage sites as World Heritage Site, a distinct and popular status assigned by the UNESCO on the fulfilment of certain criteria. Such criteria upon fulfilment designate the heritage site as a universally valuable heritage site and thus, regarded as a World Heritage Site. It is to mention here that the designation of heritage sites by UNESCO assigns a globally or universally recognized status to the concerned heritage site and thus, leadstoitspopularity.

Heritage, thus, is a social reality that is immensely significant in any society. It acts as a subject of greater interest and value. Heritage represents many and serves many. In current times, where nation-states are drawing their individual territories with much precision and distinction from each other, heritage has an upper hand in placing a nation in a dignified position with a celebrated past and a special identity. Unlike history, which is concerned with presenting a past that reveals facts, heritage on the other hand is often presented as a modified past where fact and fiction coincide to serve the interest of those who find heritage as a crucial subject to explore. Heritage is a sensitive phenomenon, that requires careful presentation when it gains popularity amongst the masses and thereby, the promotion of heritage by the State or the higher institutions should be responsibly done without affecting the interests of any community or individuals at large. Lastly, heritage first emerged in the west and ever since its emergence, it has reached every nook and corner of the world, and, practiced widely and wholeheartedly. India, too, has accepted its cultural and natural heritage as of significant national interest and thus, celebrates and promotes heritage across every geographyandsocietyintheneration.

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